

Additional information on the brown crab spider *Thomisus scrupeus* (Simon, 1886) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Peter Webb²

¹Department of Zoology, University of Venda. dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSa Gauteng team member (deceased)

Abstract: *Thomisus scrupeus* (Simon, 1886) has been recorded throughout Africa. The presence of *T. scrupeus* in South Africa is discussed, with notes on their colour variation and morphology based on live photographs. Information on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation in South Africa is provided.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). This includes several *Thomisus* specimens of which one was identified as *T. scrupeus* (Simon, 1886). *Thomisus scrupeus* was described by Simon (1886) from Senegal as *Daradius scrupeus*. It is widespread throughout Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023).

The brown crab spider differs from other African *Thomisus* species by having a granular integument, and a body covered with small polyp-like tubercles and the two pairs of front legs with thickened patellae and tibiae giving it a robust appearance. The body colour varies in the female from off-white to yellow orange to dark brown in the male. Body shape and colour vary greatly between the sexes (Figs 1–2) as well as specimens of the same sex (Figs 11–16). The body shape also varies, with the abdomen flattened (Fig. 5) to more prominent tubercles on abdomen (Fig. 15) to more rounded (Fig. 11). The variation in shape and colour have resulted in several synonyms of *T. scrupeus* such as *Thomisus caffer* Simon, 1904, *T. amanicus* Strand, 1907, *T. quadrituberculatus* Lessert, 1943, and *T. lindneri* Roewer, 1956 (World Spider Catalog, 2023).

The objective of this study is to show the variation in shape and colour based on photographs of live specimens, and the general behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa are discussed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

As part of SANSa, requests were made for photographs for the SANSa Virtual Museum and several were received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Thomisus scrupeus (Simon, 1886)

Daradius scrupeus Simon, 1886: 363

Thomisus scrupeus Comellini, 1957: 26; Jézéquel, 1964: 1121; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 17; 1988: 432; 2020: 57–58.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL females 7–8 mm, males 3–5 mm. This species differs from other species by having a granular integument, a body covered with small polyp-like tubercles (Fig. 5), and two pairs of robust front legs with thickened patellae and tibiae (Fig. 4). Female: carapace wider than long; eye tubercles flattened dorsally, sharply pointed; (Fig. 3) both eye rows recurved. Abdomen bell-shaped, usually with dark brown band between abdominal tubercles (Figs 1 & 12). Legs: legs I and II robust; with femora, tibiae, and metatarsi thickened; tibiae I and II with 3–4 pairs of short and thick macro-setae. Epigyne simple, U-shaped (Fig. 6). Male: structurally very similar to female, differs as follows: smaller; body more flattened (Fig. 2); abdomen without prominent tubercles on abdomen; macrosetae longer on tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II. Palp: large with strong retrolateral apophysis; embolus short (Fig. 7).

Figure 1–2. *Thomisus scrupeus* 1. Female. 2. Male. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–8: *Thomisus scrupeus*. 3. Eye pattern. 4. Leg I. 5. Polyp with body setae. 6. Epigyne. 7–8. Male palp. Photo credits: 3. Peter Webb. 4–7 After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Widespread throughout Africa. Recorded from Senegal, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, South Africa, Tanzania, Zaire, and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Fort Grey (-33.19, 27.12); Grahamstown, Gretna Farm (-33.3, 26.52); Idutywa (-32.1, 28.3); Kentani (-32.5, 28.32); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.206, 24.708); Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91). **Gauteng:** Cullinan Premier Game Farm (-25.67, 28.48); Moloto, Farm Enkeldoorn (-25.46, 28.63); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaa Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Irene (Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19).

KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); Lake Sibayi (-27.33, 32.68); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Shaka's Rock (-29.49, 31.24); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Zululand, Manguzi forest (-28.33, 31.08); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.54, 32.15); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.034, 32.425). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, Shabenikop, 5 km N Pretoriuskop (-22.93, 31.02); Maastroom, Farm Swellendam (-22.75, 28.43); Makalali Private Game Reserve, Pidwa (-24.16, 30.69); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Zanzibar Border Post (-22.57, 28.45); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Witrivier (-25.31, 31.02). **North West:** Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoort dam (-25.73, 27.85); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

Western Cape: Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Gouritsmond (-34.34, 21.87); Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53); Wilderness (-33.99, 22.59).

Figure 9. Known distribution of *Thomisus scrupeus* in South Africa.

Figures 10–12. *Thomisus scrupeus* female. 9. Female in retreat. 10. Female on egg sac. 11. Female with spiderlings. Photo credits: 10. J. Munton-Jackson. 11-12. Peter Webb.

Female from Irene, Gauteng

Female from Bronkhorstspuit, Gauteng

Female from Irene, Gauteng

Female from Addo Elephant National Park

Female from Nwandeni, Limpopo

Female from Lephahlale, Limpopo

Male from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal

Male from Irene, Gauteng

Male from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal

Figures 11–19. *Thomisus scrupeus*. 11–16. Females. 17–19. Males. Photo credits: Peter Webb, except 14. Linda Wiese.

LIFESTYLE

Thomisus scrupeus was frequently sampled during SANSA surveys mainly while beating or sweeping vegetation. They are free-living plant dwellers and appear to be largely restricted to the shrub and tree layer. Field observations showed that the species is much more abundant in the summer months. Adult females have been sampled from December to May and males from November to January (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

The female attaches the white egg sac to a slightly curved leaf and she stays with her egg sac until the spiderlings hatch and the spiderlings are strong enough to disperse (Figs 10–12). They are frequently observed holding their front legs together as shown in Figs 22 & 23.

At the Ndumo Game Reserve, *T. scrupeus* was mainly sampled from broadleaf woodland, *Vachellia tortilis* savanna, and *V. xanthophloea* forests (Haddad *et al.*, 2006). It was also sampled in the Blouberg Nature Reserve from *Sclerocarya birrea* (Muelwala *et al.*, 2010). In orchards it was sampled in avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and citrus (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Figures 20–21. *Thomisus scrupeus* showing the typical position of the legs. Photo credits: 22. Ruan Booysen. 3. Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION STATUS

Thomisus scrupeus has a wide global distribution and is listed as Least Concern. In South Africa it is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al., 2006); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al., 2010); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2011); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al., 2016); Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2020); Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2021); Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022), and Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

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